

IMPORTANCE OF ICT IN UPGRADING AND RE-TRAINING OF STAFF AND CREATION OF A MOBILE APPLICATION FOR THE PURPOSE OF MONITORING THE PERFORMANCE OF EDUCATOR STAFF

Zaripova Dilnoz Anvarovna

Teacher of Tashkent University of Information Technologies, dotsent

Kuvandikova Feruza Muzaffar qizi

He is a student of the Faculty of ICT in the ICT field of TATU

named after Muhammad al-Khorazimi

quvondiqovaferuza1@gmail.com

Tursunova Muxlisa Maxamadjon qizi

He is a student of the Faculty of ICT in the ICT field of TATU

named after Muhammad al-Khorazimi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7277922>

Abstract. This article describes the importance of using the latest ICT tools in training and improving the skills of qualified, knowledgeable personnel, and about the mobile application for the purpose of monitoring the personnel's work on their own.

Key words: ICT, non-governmental, professional, qualification, category, modern assessment, Java, Kotlin, programming languages.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ИКТ В ПОВЫШЕНИИ И ПЕРЕПОДГОТОВКЕ КАДРОВ И СОЗДАНИИ МОБИЛЬНОГО ПРИЛОЖЕНИЯ ДЛЯ МОНИТОРИНГА ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ КАДРОВ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассказывается о важности использования новейших средств ИКТ в обучении и повышении квалификации квалифицированного, знающего персонала, а также о мобильном приложении с целью самостоятельного контроля работы персонала.

Ключевые слова: ИКТ, негосударственный, профессиональный, квалификация, категория, современная оценка, Java, Kotlin, языки программирования.

INTRODUCTION

2021 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan in order to further increase the level and quality of retraining of pedagogic personnel and their qualification, to strengthen its teaching-methodical and information supply, to provide the republic's educational institutions with highly qualified pedagogic personnel - Resolution No. 243 of April 27, 2021 and No. 572 of September 17, 2021 "On measures to improve the procedure for certification of pedagogic staff of preschool, general secondary, special secondary, professional and extracurricular educational organizations" based on the decision, at the same time, according to the state program on the implementation of the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 in the "Year of supporting youth and strengthening the health of the population", from January 1, 2022: preschool, general secondary, secondary special, professional and school The practice of creating attestation commissions for the attestation of pedagogic personnel of foreign educational institutions and submitting documents through a collective file was canceled, and the attestation of pedagogic personnel was carried out by the State Inspectorate of Educational Quality under the Cabinet of

Ministers for the assessment of their pedagogical skills and psychological preparation. it was decided that it will be carried out by conducting a qualification test.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

The regulation on the procedure for the examination of pedagogic personnel of pre-school, general secondary, secondary special, professional and extracurricular educational organizations was approved, which provides for the following: assessment of pedagogical skills and psychological preparation of pedagogic personnel and testing of their qualifications in educational subjects, state service centers, Unified online acceptance of teachers' documents through the portal of interactive state services or the official website of the Education Inspectorate, issuing to teachers an electronic certificate with an electronic signature and a QR code. Our words have been proven in such decisions.

Information and communication technologies (ICT) play an increasingly important role in our modern lives, for example, in communication and learning. Before explaining the importance of ICT curricula, let's first explain what exactly these concepts entail. For starters, ICT stands for information and communication technology and consists of several different components such as software, communication systems, and online data sharing systems. Nowadays, if people do not have basic information about these components, they will not be able to achieve their goals and may be cut off from the modern world. This is where ICT training programs come into play. No matter how much or how little education a person has, these training programs ensure that they are fully prepared to enter the world of work.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Further development of our developing country, further development of lifestyle is in the hands of the future youth, the educators of the future generation are the people who educate them to perfection in every way, and the professionals are our pedagogues and teachers. Therefore, it is clear from the above decisions that great attention is being paid to the pedagogical personnel who educate the next generation, to work on themselves, to improve their qualifications, to acquire new knowledge suitable for the time, at the same time, this measure is to control the pedagogical personnel within the activities. certification exams are held from time to time in order to control the work of pedagogical personnel. The purpose of this is to select experienced, knowledgeable, dynamic pedagogical personnel, encourage them to work on themselves, and encourage them to apply new methods and innovations in practice.

In the process of training and retraining of teachers, we developed the following program and received practical results in training institutes. The program is written in Java, Kotlin languages, it includes all specialized subjects. This application is intended for teachers, with answers to certification tests in all subjects installed, after completing the tests, the application shows the user the total number of correct answers, the user can analyze the test questions and work on his mistakes. It gives an opportunity to work on the downloaded tests, which work easily without Internet connection through the mobile application.

Disadvantages: It is designed only for teachers of the Uzbek language, it is designed only for school teachers.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, ICT training programs are very important, especially in areas where the digital divide is widespread. The goal of gaining knowledge on ICT and using it in practice is to increase the qualification of personnel and to apply new knowledge in practice. This application,

developed for this purpose, creates wide opportunities for pedagogical personnel. The program can be used anytime anywhere as in the mobile application and further improvements to the application can be made.

REFERENCES

1. Law of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" dated September 23, 2020.
2. The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On further improvement of the system of retraining and professional development of pedagogues"
3. "Java" book of the Seventh Edition.